

RESEARCH ARTICLE

On- and Off-Campus Mentoring Expectations of the Pre-Service Teachers from their Cooperating Teachers: The School of Education Experience

Sol G. Simbulan, Ph.D.
Carmelyn M. Ole

School of Education, San Isidro College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon

Correspondence to: solsimbulan@gmail.com; cole@sic.edu.ph

Received: May 1, 2021; **Accepted:** May 7, 2021

ABSTRACT

The central theme of this study is on the mentoring expectations of the 16 pre-service teachers of San Isidro College from their cooperating teachers during the academic year 2019-2020, as they journeyed into their practice teaching both in-campus and out-campus training. The study utilized the descriptive method of research employing a researcher-made questionnaire highlighting on the four areas on mentoring. Findings revealed that pre-service teachers *highly expected* to be mentored by their cooperating teachers in the area on classroom management and preparation of forms and reports. They *expected* to be mentored in the different phases of instruction and in school activities. They expected assistance in the making of lesson objectives, giving motivational techniques, presentation of the lesson, questioning techniques, preparation of instructional materials, doing assessment, classroom structuring, and awareness on the DepEd thrusts. Finally, they considered their cooperating teachers as primarily a coach and a mentor.

Key words: *Mentoring expectations, Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs), Cooperating Teachers (CTs)*

INTRODUCTION

The roles of the Supervising Teachers, known also this time as the Cooperating Teachers (CTs) provide an important impact in the mentoring expectations of the Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs) who experience the mentee-mentor relationship during their on and off campus practice-teaching. This mentoring relationship between the beginning teacher (PST) and the seasoned teacher (CT) facilitates the transmission of knowledge, skills, values and culture that the PSTs need in their pursuit of becoming teachers. Cooperating teachers were known before as “critic teachers” which had more of a negative connotation as persons inclined to notice faults, flaws and imperfections of the PSTs.

During the practice-teaching where the PSTs observe, assist and teach the classes of their “critic teachers,” they are anxious and nervous as beginner teachers because they will be evaluated by the critic

teachers. However, this time the title “critic teacher” is changed to “cooperating teachers” which has a positive connotation, where CTs serve as tutors or guide to the PSTs in becoming efficient and effective teachers in the future.

San Isidro College started to offer the Bachelor of Secondary Education in 1965 and the Bachelor of Elementary Education in 1993. The Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs) of each batch have their on-campus practice teaching in the Elementary and High School Departments of San Isidro College. These departments are the Integrated Basic Education (IBED) for four years now. The off-campus student teaching is in the Department of Education Cooperating Schools in the Bukidnon Division years back and in the Malaybalay City Division when this was established since September 1, 2009.

The student teachers, now, the Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs) are under the supervision and

guidance of their Cooperating Teachers (CTs). With the different phases of the practice teaching, the Pre-Service Teachers experience the assistance and mentoring that required planning, time management, dedication and feedbacking from their CTs to hone them into better potential teachers.

The Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs) have role expectations from their Cooperating Teachers (CTs). They consider their CTs as their role models of effective and efficient teachers. The PSTs have the notion that their CTs guide and assist them in their teacher training. The PSTs submit their lesson plans for the CTs to check and give suggestions on what to do during actual teaching. They prepare instructional materials as suggested by their CTs and do structuring of bulletin boards. They assist in the classroom management and in the disciplining of the students/pupils. They check and monitor attendance. They help the CTs in the maintenance of the classroom cleanliness and orderliness. They assist in the preparation of test papers, recording of the results and even computing of the students' grades. Practically, the Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs) undergo the teacher training in the actual learning and teaching environment. These trainings are needed and beneficial for the PSTs to handle their classes in the future.

The way the PSTs view the roles of their Cooperating Teachers and what they expect from them will help the School of Education at San Isidro

College improve the practices of the CTs. It is therefore the aim of this study to investigate the mentoring expectations of the PSTs from their Cooperating Teachers (CTs) both in the on and off-campus practice teaching during the Academic year 2019-2020.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Head, Reiman and Thies-Sprinthall (1992) postulate that the “heart and soul “of mentoring grows out of belief “in the value and worth of people and an attitude toward education that focuses upon passing the torch to the next generation of teachers.” The mentoring process extends far beyond supporting the induction of new teachers into the school system through professional guidance and encouragement. Shadiow (1996) believes that the heart of mentorship comes from a commitment to education, a hope for its future, and a respect for those who enter into its community. Accordingly, the major aspects that contribute to the complexity of mentoring include the multiple needs of beginning teachers as well as their mentors, their developmental issues or concerns, their repertoire of teaching skills, the school culture that may impact positively or negatively on the mentoring process, and numerous other variables

The roles of the Cooperating Teachers (CTs) in mentoring the Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs) are varied (Good, 1987; Barr, 1952). Teachers are considered facilitators of learning, counsellor of students/pupils and leaders in the community. Their roles are not only

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

associated with instruction but also on counselling activity (Amidon and Hunter, 1967). Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study.

The Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs) expect their Cooperating Teachers (CTs) to help them in their Practice Teaching. There are several mentoring expectations of the PSTs from their CTs. These include phases of instruction, classroom management, preparation of forms, and school activities. The PSTs expect their CTs to help them in their lesson presentation and choice of instructional materials. These are areas in their practice teaching that they find most difficult and they expect their CTs to mentor them in these areas.

Aside from the different phases of instruction, the PSTs expect their CTs to help the PSTs to maintain classroom discipline. The PSTs find classroom management a difficult part of their practice-teaching since they do not want the students to fear them. The PSTs need to practice their skills in time management, class management and class discipline with their CTs' help. The PSTs also need their CTs to help them in assessing the students through tests and other alternative forms to measure the learning objectives set and how to give points to the test. Another concern of the PSTs is on structuring the classrooms, when they have to consider what to put/mount in the bulletin boards and to seek the approval of their CTs prior the display of materials.

The Department of Education (DepEd) closely monitored the practice teaching programs of TEIs, especially because most of the graduates are absorbed by DepEd. The PSTs are bound to incorporate the trends and thrusts of the department. They have to be familiar with the accomplishments of forms required by DepEd. These forms could be cumbersome if the PSTs do not know how to fill them up.

CTs also introduce several activities to the PSTs to prepare them for their future encounters with these. Sometimes CTs ask the PSTs to do some coaching with students for contests thus preparing them for the task on student mentoring in the future. CTs prepare PSTs for routine classroom activities and for other co-curricular activities that they will meeting in the future when they become teachers.

The PSTs have also great mentoring expectations from their CTs especially on the preparation of their lesson plans; the writing of lesson objectives; employing motivational techniques; their lesson

presentation; the questioning techniques; the choices and preparation of IMs; the assessment techniques; classroom structuring; and knowledge on DepEd thrusts. The PSTs believed that these are fundamental concerns that they need to know and become familiar with to prepare them for their future career.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study investigated the mentoring expectations of the Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs) from their Supervising/Cooperating Teachers (CTs) both in the on- and off-campus practice teaching during the Academic Year 2019-2020.

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What are the mentoring expectations of the Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs) from their Cooperating Teachers (CTs) in their on and off-campus practice teaching in the following:
 - 1.1 phases of instruction;
 - 1.2 classroom management;
 - 1.3 preparation of forms and reports; and
 - 1.4 school activities?
2. What are the PSTs' expectations from their CTs in mentoring them in:
 - 2.1 lesson objectives;
 - 2.2 motivational techniques;
 - 2.3 lesson presentation;
 - 2.4 questioning techniques;
 - 2.5 choices of instructional materials (IMs);
 - 2.6 assessment techniques;
 - 2.7 classroom structuring; and
 - 2.8 DepEd Thrusts?
3. What are the perceptions of the PSTs on the role of their CTs?

METHODOLOGY

The venue of this study is at San Isidro College, which offers the Teacher Education programs: The Bachelor of Secondary, majors in English, Filipino, Mathematics and Values Education and Bachelor of Elementary Education. San Isidro College has for its flagship the formation of men and women of prayer and for others.

The participants of this study are the 16 PSTs where ten (10) came from the Bachelor of Secondary Education and six (6) from the Bachelor of Elementary Education Pre-Service Teachers during

the AY 2019-2020. Considering that they were only 16, they were purposively chosen for this study.

The study utilized a questionnaire prepared by the proponents for the PSTs to answer. It consists of three parts to answer the problems set in the study. Part I contains the mentoring expectations of the PSTs from their CTs. These are categorized into four components namely: Phases of Instructions with 10 items, Classroom Management with 10 items, Preparation of Forms and Reports with 5 items and School Activities with 10 items. The criteria used the following:

3 (1.4-3.0)	Highly Expected	When one expects at all times.
2 (0.7-1.3)	Less Expected	When one expects sometimes
1 (0.1-0.6)	Not Expected	When one do not expect at all

Part II is composed of open-ended questions on the PSTs' opinion or ideas on the ways their CTs can help them to write the lesson objectives, motivational techniques, lesson presentation, questioning techniques, choice of IMs, assessment techniques, classroom structuring and DepEd thrusts.

Part III asked on the perceptions of the PSTs on the role of their CTs as mentors during their Practice Teaching.

The proponents administered the questionnaire to the PSTs after the on-campus and off-campus Practice Teaching. The responses were tallied, analyzed and interpreted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Mentoring expectations of pre-service teachers from their cooperating teachers

Table 1 shows the results of the mentoring expectations of pre-service teachers on the phases of instruction employed by the cooperating teachers. The overall mean indicates that the PSTs expect their CTs to mentor them on the indicators in this area. The overall standard deviation shows that their ratings are homogeneous indicating that these are close to each other. From the individual ratings of the indicators, the PSTs highly expected their CTs to mentor them on “what motivational techniques would be appropriate for a particular lesson; what steps and procedures should be undertaken in the lesson; and what instructional materials would be appropriate”. These findings indicate that PSTs wanted to know how to proceed with the lesson particularly on motivational techniques, steps for the lesson presentation, and appropriate instructional materials to use in their lesson.

Larkin (2013) stated that learning to teach is stressful and challenging for student teachers to integrate their own ideas about good teaching with

Table 1. Results of the evaluation of pre-service teachers on the phases of instruction employed by the cooperating teachers in mentoring

AREA 1 - Phases of instruction

Cooperating Teachers should mentor/suggest to Pre-service teachers on...

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank	Qualitative Description
What motivational techniques would be appropriate for a particular lesson?	2.62	0.15	1	Highly Expected
How to write behavioral objectives of the lesson	2.31	0.13	7.5	Expected
How to prepare the lesson plan for the day	2.31	0.13	7.5	Expected
What instructional materials would be appropriate	2.43	0.14	3	Highly expected
How to present the lesson	2.37	0.13	4.5	Expected
What steps and procedures should be undertaken in the lesson	2.50	0.14	2	Highly Expected
How to prepare and ask higher order questions	2.37	0.13	4.5	Expected
What alternative assessment could be used in the lesson	2.18	0.12	10	Expected
What activities are appropriate for the lesson	2.31	0.13	7.5	Expected
What assignments should be given for the lesson	2.31	0.13	7.5	Expected
OVERALL	2.37	0.13		EXPECTED

those of their teacher education programs. He mentioned 10 tips for mentoring student teachers such as teachers should not leave them alone and model how to teach in a constructive manner. In this way teachers could mentor student teachers to let them have creative outlets. They could model on how to motivate the class with their motivational techniques, what steps they should take when presenting a lesson, and what instructional materials to prepare.

The item that has the least rating was on “what alternative assessment could be used in the lesson”. The mentoring of this aspect was expected by the PSTs, although from among the list of expectation this concern was rated least. It could be because they have more pressing concern with the other issues thus prioritizing them more than this. Besides, they could tackle this issue later on after they make their objectives and lesson plans. The presumptions that assessment is at the end of their lesson presentations make them also feel that this is not their urgent priority.

Table 2 presents the results of the mentoring expectations of PSTs on the classroom management employed by the CTs. The overall mean indicates that the PSTs highly expect that their CTs mentor them on

the indicators in this area. The overall standard deviation shows that their ratings are not dispersed indicating that these are close to each other. From the ten individual ratings of the indicators, there were six items that the student teachers highly expected their CTs to mentor them. Among the top three indicators were on “how to avoid student bullying and other deviant behaviors; how to implement classroom discipline; how to maintain and sustain order in the classroom; and how they can gain respect from their pupils”. These indicators are really causing anxiety on the part of the PSTs. Classroom management is a problem when students are difficult to handle. When the PSTs could not put order in the classroom then they could not facilitate their lesson objectives and plans. There are times when students are noisy and the PSTs’ could not control them anymore making them very anxious as to how the CTs would rate them on this aspect.

These indicators really could cause problems to student teachers especially that they are still new and very idealistic. They expect the pupils/students to be attentive, disciplined, courteous, polite and obedient. But, their expectations may not be the reality in the actual classroom setting. There could be children bullying; there could be problems in discipline;

Table 2. Results of the evaluation of pre-service teachers on the Classroom Management employed by the cooperating teachers in mentoring

AREA 2 – Classroom Management				
<i>Cooperating Teachers should mentor/suggest to Pre-service teachers on...</i>	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank	Qualitative Description
When to check attendance and how to prevent tardiness and absences	2.31	0.13	9	Expected
How routine tasks are done e.g. greetings, entrance and exit in classes, passing of papers, etc.	2.37	0.14	7.5	Expected
What are the school rules and policies for different offenses	2.43	0.14	6	Highly Expected
What other housekeeping tasks are to be done	2.06	0.11	10	Expected
What attitude/behaviors are expected from student teachers	2.56	0.15	5	Highly Expected
How to implement classroom discipline	2.68	0.15	2	Highly Expected
How to maintain and sustain order in the classroom	2.62	0.15	3.5	Highly Expected
How to maintain cleanliness in the classroom and surroundings	2.37	0.13	7.5	Expected
How to avoid student bullying and other deviant behaviors	2.81	0.16	1	Highly Expected
How students’ teachers can gain respect from their pupils	2.62	0.15	3.5	Highly Expected
OVERALL	2.48	0.14		HIGHLY EXPECTED

problems in how to sustain attention; and problems on how they could gain respect from the pupils/students considering that they are not the real classroom teachers. The PSTs expect help from the classroom teachers with regards to classroom management. This is not a very easy task, especially when the student teacher could not sustain pupils' interest in the lesson. Sometimes, even the real classroom teachers have problems in classroom management especially when the assigned pupils/students and sections are the ones that belong to the last section.

According to Heeralal (2014) managing a classroom is a complex process and a daunting task for a novice pre-service teacher. In order to effectively manage a class, the pre-service teacher needs to be eased into this process. During practice teaching, the PST needs the CTs to be present in the classroom to oversee how the PST could cope in handling the class. As the PST gains confidence, the CT may gradually withdraw from the classroom, allowing the mentee to manage the classroom on his/her own. Classroom management involves among other things the management of: classroom space, relationships and interactions, control, authority, discipline, system of rules and procedures, safety of learners and curriculum issues. To manage classroom well requires dedication, commitment and effort. Therefore, the role of the CT, in classroom management, is crucial in developing the PST's skills.

Table 3 illustrates the mentoring expectations of PSTs on the preparation of forms and reports employed by the CTs. The overall mean indicated that the student teachers highly expect that their CTs

mentor them in the preparation of forms used in the DepEd. These include Form 1, Form 2, and Form 138. They also highly expect that they would be mentored in the computation and transmutation of grades. Further, they highly expect that they will be mentored on how to grade pupils' work like the tests, assignments and reports. It is noted that knowing how to fill-up these forms will help the PSTs in the future especially that DepEd would require teachers to submit these forms on time.

Table 4 shows the evaluation of PSTs on the school activities employed by the CTs in mentoring. The overall mean indicates that the student teachers expected their CTs to mentor them on school activities. The first school activity in their priority to be mentored is on how to lead/conduct the Philippine National Anthem. The PSTs have seen teachers led the National anthem and they expect that they too will do the same in the near future. They are afraid that they will be asked to do this while they are on the job training.

The PSTs highly expect their CTs on how to mentor them in ensuring parents' attendance and involvement during meetings. Parents' involvement in meetings would be of great help to teachers because they could help monitor their children's performance in school as well as in the making of their projects and assignments. They could also help teachers in their children's behavior in school and prevent deviant behaviors in the classroom. Children whose parents are involved in their studies usually show good attitude and are excelling in their work and activities. CTs could assure the PSTs that parents are cooperative and they could be good partners in the

Table 3. Results of the evaluation of pre-service teachers on the Preparation of forms and reports employed by the cooperating teachers in mentoring

AREA 3– Preparation of form and reports <i>Cooperating Teachers should mentor/suggest to Pre-service teachers on...</i>	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank	Qualitative Description
How to prepare the different forms need by DepEd e.g. Form 1- school register; Form 2- Monthly Report; Form 138- Report card	2.43	0.14	2	Highly Expected
How to transmute and compute grades of the pupils	2.43	0.14	2	Highly Expected
How to grade pupils' work e.g. tests, assignments, reports	2.43	0.14	2	Highly Expected
How to prepare reports required from them	2.37	0.13	4.5	Expected
How to package their portfolio	2.37	0.13	4.5	Expected
OVERALL	2.41	0.14		HIGHLY EXPECTED

Table 4. Results of the evaluation of pre-service teachers on the school activities employed by the cooperating teachers in mentoring

AREA 4 – School Activities				
<i>Cooperating Teachers should mentor/suggest to Pre-service teachers on...</i>	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank	Qualitative Description
What to do during PTA meetings	2.37	0.14	6	Expected
What alternatives should be done to ensure parents attendance and involvement during meetings	2.43	0.14	3	Highly Expected
How to structure bulletin boards	2.18	0.12	10	Expected
What attitude are expected from student teachers when assigned to work on school related activities	2.43	0.14	3	Expected
How to budget schedules and activities	2.37	0.14	6	Expected
How to carry out school activities like coaching pupils, acting as emcees during programs, participation during school activities, etc.	2.43	0.14	3	Highly Expected
What to do during programs and convocations	2.37	0.13	6	Expected
What to do during school parties	2.31	0.13	8.5	Expected
How to conduct the Philippine National anthem during flag ceremony	2.50	0.14	1	Highly Expected
What to do during physical education activities, gardening, extension work, etc.	2.31	0.13	8.5	Expected
OVERALL	2.37	0.13		EXPECTED

education of their children to do some of their assignments and project. Once they become teachers, they could invite parents to school during PTA meetings and consultations. They could also visit their students in their homes for guidance and counseling.

The PSTs highly expect their CTs to mentor them on “how to carry out school activities like coaching pupils, acting as emcees during programs, participation during school activities, etc.”. These activities would need much confidence on the part of the PSTs such that they need the support and coaching of their CTs.

It is noted that the indicator with the least rating in this mentoring expectation is on the structuring of the bulletin board. While the PSTs expect that the CTs could mentor them in the structuring of bulletin boards, this seems to be their least priority. Many CTs just give the PSTs the topics they would like to be shown in the bulletin board and the PSTs used their creative talents to do the structuring. The CTs are usually happy when there are PSTs because these young people know how to make their bulletin boards attractive for the children.

Table 5 illustrates the summary results of the evaluation of pre-service teachers on the mentoring expectation from their cooperating instructors. From the result, it is obvious that classroom management ranked first among the mentoring concerns of the PSTs. Pre-service teachers believe that when the class is orderly and the pupils are well behaved, they can easily present their lesson and they could teach smoothly. Classroom management requires that the student teachers should have a rich repertoire of techniques on how to handle disciplinary issues. It would require them to have a personality that could command respect and attention, a voice that the pupils could hear and understand. It would require them to be firm and at the same time kind. It would require them to have mastery of their lessons and have varying techniques in teaching to sustain pupils’ interest. It would require that they should have varying instructional materials, audio visual aids, and activities to keep the pupils busy at work.

Yet, even if the student teachers have adequate instructional materials and techniques, there are really instances when classroom discipline is not attained. Here is where the cooperating teachers should come in to help the student teachers. There are instances

Table 5. *Summary results of the evaluation of pre-service teachers on the mentoring expectation from their cooperating instructors*

Areas on mentoring expectation of PSTs on their CTs	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank	Qualitative Description
Classroom Management	2.48	0.14	1	Highly Expected
Preparation of forms and reports	2.41	0.14	2	Highly Expected
Phases on Instruction	2.37	0.13	3	Expected
School Activities	2.37	0.13	4	Expected
Overall	2.41	0.13		Highly Expected

when the children would not pay attention to the PSTs knowing that these are not their real teachers. They would merely take them for granted such that they could cause chaos in the classroom. CTs need to mentor PSTs on how they could maintain order in the class. They could identify the students who are difficult to handle and would coach the PSTs on how to work with these kinds of students. Classroom management is important in order to make children learn better and appreciate how their teachers really wanted them to learn.

The PSTs are active in school activities hence this indicator has the least rating. Although they still expect the CTs to coach them on what activities to introduce or present to the class. School activities are much welcomed by the PSTs, as they are still young and eager to do extracurricular work. Since the PSTs are mostly young, they could very well relate to their students when doing co-curricular activities.

PSTs expectations of cooperating teachers' assistance in mentoring

Frame 1 illustrates the students' expectation from the supervising instructors in their assistance in making their lesson objectives. From the responses of the students, it is evident that the students expect their supervising instructors to assist and guide them in the making of their lesson objectives. In the making of the lesson plan, the CTs generally looked into the objectives of the lesson. This is the gauge on what learning will be achieved for the day's lesson and how this will be achieved. It is therefore important for the CTs to check on how the PSTs would write their lesson objectives.

The PSTs expect their CTs to check their objectives as to whether these jibe with the topic or whether these synchronize with the lesson. They wanted their CTs to even check on their grammar and sentence structures knowing fully well that they could commit mistakes on these aspects. They expected

their CTs to really check on their lesson plan, make comments and suggestions, to give feedback and be generous in giving help when they needed these.

Mentors know a great deal about teaching and learning, which often leads to a kind of practical wisdom that cannot be printed in a book – this knowledge and know-how is invaluable to new teachers. Classroom mentor is profoundly important to new teachers in their development as proficient teachers. Without mentor support new teachers can flounder and may leave a profession they have spent years studying in order to join. Mentor offers beginning teachers an anchor of support in an often challenging, demanding and sometimes chaotic transition from graduation to classroom teacher. Effective mentoring has a formative influence on the practice of beginning teachers and has a significant impact on the level and depth of learning amongst students of early career teachers (Victoria State Government, 2016).

Frame 2 shows the expectations of pre-service teachers from their cooperating teachers on how they could assist in giving motivational techniques. PSTs generally expect their CTs to give ideas on what motivational techniques are fit for the lesson. They expect them to give them varied and different examples of motivational techniques.

PSTs expect their CTs to share ideas on what motivational techniques are best for the topics and what motivational techniques are not good. They wanted their CTs to check on their motivational techniques, give comments for improvement and assist them on how to motivate. Cooperating teachers create the learning environment and can do much to motivate the PSTs. By implementing effective teaching strategies CTs can motivate the PSTs to create their motivational techniques to their students.

Frame 1. Expectations of PSTs from their CTs on how they could assist in the making of lesson objectives

Q: What is your expectations from your cooperating teachers in their assistance to your making of the Lesson Objectives?

Responses of the PSTs:

1. *My CT have meet my expectations, since she assists me in making my lesson objectives.*
2. *My CT should be very considerate.*
3. *I expect her to check every part if this is right; provide positive and negative feedback; thoughtful enough to notice mistakes for revisions.*
4. *I expect her to correct me when my lesson objective is not measurable or hard to target.*
5. *I expect her to be kind, knowledgeable and willing to share her knowledge and wisdom.*
6. *I expect more guidance and support.*
7. *I thought my CT is strict but she is not like that, example the word "identify" is not accepted by CT, but my CT suggests other terms.*
8. *Expect that she will help me to see if I am doing right.*
9. *I really ask my CT on the objectives if they are really fit.*
10. *I expect my CT to correct me if I am wrong.*
11. *My CT is very good because she has a lot of experiences.*
12. *I expect her to help me in writing my objectives especially in the affective domain that could relate to real life situations or in values education.*
13. *I expect her to remind me on the use of verbs; to deliver the objectives in a step following the learning plan.*
14. *To assist me in making lesson objectives and make these congruent/parallel to my assessment; how to make effective objectives.*
15. *To check and give comments for improvements if needed.*
16. *To Check the lesson objectives; to be generous in giving help to correct the lesson objective.*

Frame 2. Expectations of pre-service teachers from their cooperating teachers on how they could assist in giving motivational techniques

Q: What is your expectations from your cooperating teachers in their assistance in giving motivational techniques?

Responses of the PSTs:

1. *My CT should give ideas on what motivational techniques are fit for the lesson.*
2. *My CT should give more motivational techniques.*
3. *My CT should give some hints to motivate the class in the lesson proper.*
4. *I expect her to teach the techniques that I don't have.*
5. *I expect her to share her motivational techniques because this is not easy.*
6. *I expect her to give more suggestions on motivational techniques.*
7. *I expect her to give motivations that suit the lesson.*
8. *I expect her to give and share ideas on what MT are best for the topics and what MT are not good.*
9. *I expect her to motivate me and observe my motivational technique.*
10. *I expect my CT to give ideas in relation to the given topic.*
11. *To teach me something that could be used in teaching.*
12. *I expect to learn more motivational activities so that I can catch the attention of the learners.*
13. *I expect her to assist and remind me examples on motivation.*
14. *For the CT o portray or show the MT before I will start teaching.*
15. *To give ideas to fit the motivational techniques for the lesson and give comments for improvement.*
16. *For the CT to assist on how to motivate.*

Effective teaching strategies like praising and rewarding students for participating in the class discussion could be motivating. Communicating expectations to the students and coaching them how to master the materials one need to learn could help motivate the learners. Positive feedback could help motivate the learners (Ministry of Education Guyana,2020).

Frame 3 shows the Expectations of Pre-service teachers from their cooperating teachers on how they could assist in the Lesson Presentation. Presenting the lesson is one of the most anxiety-triggering activity among PSTs. To imagine themselves at the center of the class and facing the students would cause them to be nervous especially that the CTs are observing and rating them.

The PSTs expect their CTs to coach them on what to do before they present their lesson and maybe give them the assurance that they could do it. They expect that during the presentation they could be helped especially in maintaining the discipline of the students, because while they are nervous with the topic they are to present, they are also anxious on how to make the children learn. After the lesson presentation they expect that they will be given

feedback on how they present the lesson, what are their positive comments, and check on the aspects that need improvement. Mentoring PSTs on how they could present or facilitate the delivery of their lesson would greatly alleviate their fears. The lesson presentation is really their concern precisely because this is where their practice teaching centers on. Hence, mentoring on the part of the CTs would also come as a balm on the PSTs anxious spirit.

Hudson (2008) identified mentoring needs among pre-service teachers. These include understanding of system requirements e.g. curriculum, school policies and assessment; writing of lesson plans, articulate pedagogical knowledge such as teaching strategies, classroom management, motivating students and dealing with unexpected situations; and providing direct and detailed feedback about teaching performance. Hudson also suggested that mentor provide constructive guidance such as sharing teaching experiences and giving clear advice. Pre-service teachers also require constructive feedback on their teaching methods and more opportunities to teach.

Pre-service teachers need to prepare the lesson thoroughly. Preparation of a lesson ought to begin

Frame 3. Expectations of Pre-service teachers from their cooperating teachers on how they could assist in the Lesson Presentation

Q: What is your expectations from your cooperating teacher in their assistance to your Lesson Presentation?

Responses of the PSTs:

1. *I expect that my Lesson presentation will satisfy my CT.*
2. *My CT could help me deliver; and pupils are paying attention.*
3. *I expect her to give ideas on how to present a lesson without causing much time.*
4. *I expect her to correct me when my lesson objective is not measurable or hard to target.*
5. *I expect her to give prompt to make me become what she wanted me to teach.*
6. *I expect her to help in making my lesson presentation, give suggestions and in-depth analysis for the improvement of my Lesson presentation.*
7. *I expect to receive positive feedback; give advice to improve.*
8. *I expect that she will check, evaluate and have conference to improve my teaching.*
9. *CT to stay at the back; give me advise as what I need, what pictures are needed in class presentation.*
10. *I expect my CT to help me in my Lesson Presentation.*
11. *My CT is very supportive in my Lesson Presentation.*
12. *I expect her to help me in my lesson techniques in organizing the lessons.*
13. *I expect her to give me ideas on the steps in presenting the lesson.*
14. *To give me some ideas in presenting lessons especially on how to get the attention of the pupils.*
15. *To sit down with me on how to improve lesson presentation and provide positive feedback.*
16. *To assist and give feedback.*

with the identification of a suitable topic for the lesson. The topic for the lesson can be obtained from the contents of the curriculum. The teacher then needs to formulate outcomes for the lesson that are suitable and meet the needs of the learners. Other aspects that need to be considered in preparing a lesson are the previous knowledge of learners, methodology to be used to deliver the lesson, the resources needed, the content knowledge that has to be communicated/taught to learners, assessment of learners, time management, and logical lesson development (Heeralal, 2014).

During teaching practice, the pre-service teacher must consult with his/her cooperating teacher for assistance in enhancing the quality of a lesson that is being prepared. Sufficient time needs to be budgeted/allocated for lesson preparation. Underestimation of the time taken to prepare a lesson can be a serious drawback in preparing and presenting a successful lesson. In preparing a lesson a teacher needs to find out what the learners already know, what the curriculum requirements are, what outcomes need to be achieved, what strategies or method will be used to achieve these outcomes, what new knowledge will be acquired by learners and what assessment strategies will be used to ascertain whether the knowledge has been acquired by the

learners, what activities the learners will be involved in and what resources are available (Heeralal, 2014).

Frame 4 presents the expectations of pre-service teachers from their cooperating teachers on how they could assist in the questioning techniques used. The type of questions raised in the classroom would have many implications on the students' learning. If they are merely exposed to lower-order category questions, this would imply that they are only developing the lower-order thinking skills. There is a need for CTs to really mentor the PSTs on how to prepare their questions such that these would have a good representation of both the lower order and the higher order thinking skills.

The PSTs could be guided as to how to prepare higher-order thinking skills questions. They should be mentored in writing and preparing their questions before they present their lessons, so that they would not be merely asking lower-order questions. CTs could mentor them even in the techniques in asking questions. They could utilize some activities for students' involvement and participation during class discussions.

Frame 5 shows the expectations of pre-service teachers from their cooperating teachers on how they could assist in the use of instructional materials. The choice and preparation of instructional materials

Frame 4. Expectations of pre-service teachers from their cooperating teachers on how they could assist in the questioning techniques used

Q: What is your expectations from your cooperating teachers in their assistance to your questioning techniques?

Responses of the PSTs:

1. *I expect my CT to help me improve my questioning techniques.*
2. *For me to ask appropriate and convenient to the pupils.*
3. *I expect her to encourage me to ask appropriate questions.*
4. *I expect her to teach socratic questioning skills.*
5. *I expect her to share knowledge on how to give HOTS questions.*
6. *I need guidance to make questions in the HOTS.*
7. *To ask questions that pupils can readily think...critical thinking skills.*
8. *Help me to have pre-conference/sharing some questions and questioning techniques related to the topic.*
9. *Help me improve my questioning techniques.*
10. *I expect my CT to appreciate and give comments on my questioning techniques.*
11. *Help me in the art of questioning.*
12. *I expect her to help me learn some questions that develop HOTS.*
13. *I expect her to give ideas on questioning techniques.*
14. *I expect her to have conference with me after class on my questioning techniques.*
15. *Questioning techniques must be supervised by the CTs.*
16. *Give possible samples of questioning techniques.*

could be taxing to the PSTs especially because they have other pressing activities to consider while on practice teaching. There are PSTs who have the creativity to prepare their IMs however there are those who find these cumbersome and difficult. CTs have to be understanding to their PSTs on this regard. They have to consider that PSTs have financial problems to consider and buying materials to construct their IMs would add to their other burdens. Hence, some CTs are kind to share some of their available IMs for the PSTs to use. In this way, they could simply coach them on how to prepare these materials so that in the future they could have their own.

There are instances where the CTs would really let the PSTs construct such IMs because they could utilize these in many subject areas when they will teach in the future. The PSTs expect the CTs to mentor them on how to make simple instructional materials and to make suggestions as to the appropriateness of their use.

In today's generation of students, they are more adept on the use of technology in presenting their lessons. They could easily create PowerPoint presentations or they could surf the internet on the topic that they are to present and inject these in their

lessons. They could make simulations in the computer and they could use videos and films to motivate their learners and to make them have a clearer understanding of the lesson. The CTs could guide the PSTs as to what they could present in their PowerPoint and in their videos. These presentations have to be supervised by the CTs so that errors will be corrected.

Frame 6 shows the expectations of pre-service teachers from their cooperating teachers on how they could assist them in their assessments of the students. Assessment is very important in teaching. It gauges the kind of teaching the PSTs deliver and the learning their students get from them. Hence, the PSTs wanted to learn how they could prepare assessment tools for their students, how to make their assessment tools valid and reliable, and how to conduct their assessment materials. CTs have different ways and techniques of assessing the students. They could mentor the PSTs on what assessments they are to prepare and how to prepare them.

The PSTs are willing to learn from their CTs on how they could prepare their assessment, what they need to do, and what feedback they need to improve on. The PSTs know that they are novice in

Frame 5. Expectations of pre-service teachers from their cooperating teachers on how they could assist in the instructional materials used

Q: What is your expectations from your cooperating teachers in their assistance in the instructional materials used?

Responses of the PSTs:

1. I expect my CT to help me met her expectation in the preparation of IMs.
2. To guide me in the preparation of IMs and to provide IMs.
3. I expect her to guide me in the presentation of IMs to get the attention of the pupils.
4. To give ideas on visual aids to be used.
5. To allow me to use IMs and technology.
6. To give me comments and suggestions on good IMs to assess learning.
7. To suggest practical IMs, and simple IMs.
8. To help me in checking my IMs before and after the class.
9. To guide me in the visual aids to be used in the lower grades and PowerPoint in the higher grades.
10. To suggest what IMs to be used.
11. To provide IMs for convenience.
12. I expect her to teach me new IMs that could fit all learners.
13. I expect her to allow me to us IMs on my own for my lessons.
14. I expect her to help me choose the IMs to use in the lesson.
15. Help me improve by checking ahead of time the IMs to use for better presentation.
16. To be supportive to my teaching.

teaching and making assessments, hence mentoring from their CTs would be a great help for them.

CTs can share best practices regarding assessment with the pre-service teacher. Interpretation and practical implementation of assessment policies occur in the classroom. The mentor needs to “show the student the ropes’ of learner assessment (Heeralal, 2014)

are essential, hence CTs should mentor PSTs on how to do these.

Frame 8 illustrates the expectations of pre-service teachers from their cooperating teachers on their assistance in mentoring them on the DepEd thrusts. Generally, CTs have a repertoire of the DepEd thrusts for PSTs to learn and be familiar with. Since many of the PSTs would apply for a teaching

Frame 6. Expectations of Pre-service teachers from their cooperating teachers on assessment

Q: What is your expectations from your cooperating teachers in their assistance in mentoring you on assessment?

Responses of the PSTs:

1. *I expect my CT to provide feedback on my assessment tool.*
2. *I expect her to check my evaluation before introducing to the class.*
3. *I expect her to provide best assessment tools.*
4. *I expect her to teach me techniques in assessing students.*
5. *To teach me to facilitate assessment.*
6. *To give me varied assessment techniques.*
7. *To help me make collaborative and individual assessment.*
8. *To help me in reviewing and checking my assessment tools.*
9. *(no response)*
10. *(no response)*
11. *To give me the chance to create my own assessment tool.*
12. *I expect her to teach me examples of effective assessment.*
13. *I expect her to help me assess the learning of the pupil.*
14. *I expect her to show and give assessment techniques.*
15. *Help me to read and study ahead of time.*
16. *Open and willing to share assessment materials.*

Frame 7 illustrates the expectations of pre-service teachers from their cooperating teachers on how they could assist in the classroom structuring. The PSTs are generally young and would love to structure and decorate the classroom for the students to learn and for the CTs to appreciate. However, the structuring of classroom bulletin boards is not merely decorating this but showcasing the relevant themes of the lesson for the week or the month. It can feature the works and activities done by the students. It can show the important and current events that the teacher would like the students to learn and remember. It can also show the quotes of the day or the week, the assignments of the students in cleaning their room, the birthday celebrants for the month, and other important data that will interest the students. CTs generally ask the PSTs to structure the bulletin board monthly as these would require time to prepare and even financial expenses on their part. Simple but meaningful and relevant structuring of bulletin boards

job at the DepEd, it would be essential if the CTs already orient them on the different DepEd thrusts so they become familiar with these.

DepEd have several thrusts and programs related to teaching and learning; protection of environment; nutrition program; waste management program; no children left behind program; reading program; mathematics program and other subject areas program. It would be good for the PSTs to learn about these thrusts and programs so they will be familiar with them and they could also be updated and kept abreast with these thrusts. Knowing these would also prepare them for their LET exams because there could be DepEd circulars and memoranda on these thrusts that could be included in the exam.

Pre-service teachers’ perception on the role of the cooperating teachers

Frame 7. Expectations of pre-service teachers from their cooperating teachers on how they could assist in the classroom structuring

Q: What is your expectations from your cooperating teachers in their assistance in the classroom structuring?

Responses of the PSTs:

1. *I expect my CT to help me decorate the bulletin board*
2. *To assist me in classroom structuring*
3. *To tell me where to designated properly the postcards and other learning materials*
4. *To teach me how to be creative in classroom structuring*
5. *To show me how to do classroom structuring and to learn more on classroom structuring*
6. *Help me to learn classroom structuring*
7. *Monitor the work well*
8. *To help me to make a better classroom structuring*
9. *(no response)*
10. *To suggest strategies in classroom structuring*
11. *Give me the chance to do classroom structuring*
12. *I expect her to teach me how to structure the bulletin board*
13. *I expect her to be with me when doing the structuring*
14. *I expect her to teach me how to structure the board based from DepEd*
15. *Supervise in the classroom structuring*
16. *Supportive in the work of the students in classroom structuring*

Frame 8. Expectations of pre-service teachers from their cooperating teachers on their assistance in mentoring them on the DepEd Thrusts

Q: What is your expectations from your cooperating teachers in their assistance in mentoring them on the DepEd Thrusts?

Responses of the PSTs:

1. *I expect my CT to help me teach the pupils to be respectful*
2. *To introduce me to the DepEd thrusts*
3. *I expect her to guide me on how to incorporate the DepEd thrust in classroom teaching*
4. *To give us the DepEd matters applied in the classroom*
5. *Teach me some activities from DepEd and how to used these*
6. *Help me develop and instill DepEd thrusts in my teaching*
7. *Dep Ed Thrusts are challenging both public and private schools*
8. *To have conference on DepEd thrusts and expectations*
9. *(no response)*
10. *(no response)*
11. *That DepEd could help me to do more and support my teaching*
12. *To help m learn some DepEd thrusts*
13. *To learn more on modules and curriculum guided from DepEd*
14. *To learn some DepEd policies*
15. *To guide me on the DepEd thrust as guidance for the improvement in my teaching and make me a better teacher*
16. *To teach me about the DepEd thrusts*

Matrix 1 shows the responses of the student teachers' perceptions on the role of the supervising instructor and the corresponding roles that are depicted from their perceptions. From the list of

possible roles that the student teachers characterize the roles of their supervising teachers, eight roles surfaced out. These roles include: coach (13), mentor

(10), motivator (6), teacher (5), guide (5), friend (5), inspirer (4), supervisor (3), and critic (2).

Based from their perceptions, it is observed that the pre-service teacher considers their cooperating teacher primarily as a coach and a mentor. It is noted that their perceptions of their cooperating teachers' roles could be overlapping or a combination of several roles. One could very well describe the roles of CTs as multifaceted. Thirteen students perceived their supervising instructors as a coach, while 10 students perceived them as mentors. It could be said that every teaching position includes an element of coaching. An instructional coach usually sits at the back of the classroom and observes classes, takes notes on how the student teacher runs the lessons, connects with the pupils, asks questions, and how the pupils respond. At the end of the session, the coach debriefs the lesson, discuss what the teacher did well

and what needs improvement, and give specific steps for the teacher to do for the next lesson. This method of observation, reflection, and debriefing is at the core of many instructional coaching strategies. Coaching supervising instructors usually involves being in the classroom with the student teachers, helping them set their goals, improve their teaching techniques and giving them advices (Diamond, A., 2003)

According to Domanski (2019) there are ten top traits of great coaches. Teachers as coaches should have these characteristics or traits like: organized and committed; have consistency and is process-oriented; give participated feedback; objective; knowledgeable and skilled; give balanced and fair feedback; flexible and adjustable; patient and tolerant; tough and fair; and are realistic. The actual coaching process with the student teachers is consistent such that they are not left confused on the methodology of the supervising

Matrix 1. Student teachers perception on the role of the supervising instructors

PST	Responses of pre-service teachers' perceptions on the role of the Cooperating teachers	Roles manifested by the CTs
1.	That she will see all my efforts as a student teacher	supervisor; inspirer; motivator; coach; mentor
2.	Teaches me a lot of her experiences as a part of my growth	teacher, mentor, coach
3.	Serves as a light to guide my way in my teaching life	inspirer; guide; motivator, friend
4.	Is open to us so we can immerse ourselves in teaching	guide; coach; friend
5.	Provides knowledge that can boost our confidence	teacher, mentor, coach, motivator
6.	Mentors my teaching	mentor, teacher, coach
7.	Is very supportive and approachable	friend, coach, mentor; motivator
8.	Monitors me	supervisor, mentor, coach, critic
9.	Guides/corrects/helps me in my lesson presentation and classroom management	guide, critic, coach, mentor, supervisor, teacher
10.	A mentor	mentor, teacher, coach
11.	A Guide	guide, coach
12.	Guide me during my practice teaching	guide, coach
13.	Supportive in my teaching and in everything	friend, coach, mentor; motivator
14.	Help me become a competitive teacher	friend, coach, mentor; motivator
15.	Help me in improving myself to grow better	inspirer; guide; motivator
16.	Is enthusiastic and optimistic in the teaching practice	inspirer; guide; motivator

instructor. Good coaching has four key components, namely: standards, monitoring, analysis, and feedback. Cooperating teachers as coaches are knowledgeable. They know the teaching strategies, instructional materials and assessment. They know the processes - the skills and techniques that contribute to success in teaching. The skills combined with knowledge create a success.

Supervising instructors as mentors usually focus on helping the student teachers get better for their benefit and well-being. They find personal satisfaction in seeing their student teachers succeed and genuinely develop them. Mentors have recognizable competence and expertise. They possess a great combination of toughness and compassion and they believe that their student teachers could perform well as future teachers (Reiland, D., 2019).

Some student teachers also perceived the roles of cooperating teachers as motivators, teachers, guide, and friend. As a motivator, the cooperating teachers have the role of giving positive feedback, giving praises and encouragements, and urging them to move forward and never quit. They lead the students to reach higher goals and objectives, giving them examples on how they could improve in their teaching.

The cooperating teachers' roles as a teacher, guide, and friend ranked 5th from among the students perceived roles. In these roles, the pre-service teachers perceived their CTs to teach and guide them just like a friend. They believed that the CTs should guide them on what to do, so that they will not make mistakes. They wanted their CTs to be friendly with them so that they would not feel the pressures and stress in their practice teaching. Oftentimes, when their CTs are friendly and kind, students gain confidence and lessen their fear. Pre-service teachers who are practicing on how to teach would find themselves awkward and inadequate, the reason why CTs should be calm, kind, and professionally friendly in teaching them.

There were PSTs who still perceived their CTs as a supervisor and a critic, although only a few of them think that they should be. These students believed that there should be an element of strict supervision and critiquing so that they could learn on how to improve their teaching practice. Sometimes the element of fear and the recognition that the CT is a person of authority and respect could make the students learn better. The criticisms the CTs gave could challenge

them to check on their work and enhance them to become better.

In a nutshell, PSTs perceptions of the roles of their CTs are varied, although their prevailing concept is the role of mentoring and coaching.

CONCLUSION

The mentoring of the CTs to the PSTs in the on- and off-campus practice teaching is a complex and multi-dimensional process of guiding, teaching, influencing and supporting a beginning pre-service teacher. The PSTs expect their cooperating teacher to mentor, lead, guide and advise them during their on- and off- campus practice teaching. As Feiman-Nemser and Parker (1992) said, the CTs can ably share teaching methods/strategies, materials and other resources; help solve problems in teaching and learning; provide personal and professional support; explain school policies, regulations and procedures; and guide the growth of the PSTs through reflection, collaboration, and shared inquiry.

Mentoring PSTs at the outset contributes to acquiring better teachers in the school system. Well-mentored PSTs in the on-and off- campus practice teaching could be the key to the transformation of schools that could "lead to enriched professional development experiences" (Dilworth and Imig, 1995).

The School of Education at San Isidro College provided the PSTs with a strong start for their future teaching careers journeying with them in their on-and off-campus practice teaching; while the cooperating teachers who served as mentors could get the ripple effect of success as being a part of the PSTs transformation.

REFERENCES

- Amidon, E. and Hunter, E. (1967). *Improving Teaching :The Analysis of Classroom Verbal Interaction*. New York : Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Barr, A.S. (1952). *Teaching Competencies*. In W.S Monroe (Ed.). *Encyclopedia of Educational Research*, New York : Mac Millan.
- Dilworth, Mary E. and Imig, David G. (1995). Professional Teacher Development. *The Eric Review*, v3, n3, 5-11.
- Diamond, A. (2003). *Coaching vs Mentoring as a teacher*. Retrieved from

- <https://study.com/academy/lesson/coaching-vs-mentoring-as-a-teacher.html>
- Domanski, J. (2019). *Top 10 traits of great coaching*. Retrieved from https://www.iidmglobal.com/expert_talk/expert-talk-categories/leadership/coach_mentor
- Experiential Learning Course Handbook (2009) Commission on Higher Education
- Feiman-Nemser, Sharon and Parker, Michelle B. (Spring 1992). *Mentoring in Context: A Comparison of Two U. S. Programs for Beginning Teachers*. NCRTL Special Report. East Lansing, MI: National Center for Research on Teacher Learning, Michigan State University, ED 346 091.
- Good, T.L. (1987). *Teachers expectations*. In D.C. Berliner and B.V. Rosenshine (Eds). *Talks to teachers*, New York : Random House
- Heeralal, Dr. PJH (2014). Mentoring Needs of pre-Service Teachers During Teaching Practice. A Case Study at a South African University, *Journal of Educational and Social Research* MCSER Publishing, Rome-Italy Vol. 4 No.1 January 2014 511 ISSN 2239-978X ISSN 2240
- Hudson, P.B. & Nguyen, Thi. H. (2008) *What do preservice EFL teachers expect from their mentors?*, Australian Association of Research in Education (AARE) Conference 2008, 30th November - 4th December, 2008, Brisbane
- Head, Fay A., Reiman, Alan J. and Thies-Sprinthall, Lois (1992). *The Reality of Mentoring: Complexity in Its Process and Function. Mentoring: Contemporary Principles and Issues*. ed. Bey, Theresa & Holmes, C. Thomas. Reston, VA: Association of Teacher Educators.
- Koki, Stan (1994). The Role of Teacher Mentoring in Educational Reform. Pacific Resource for Education and Learning. PREL Briefing Paper. Retrieved from <https://www.nmu.edu/Webb/ArchivedHTML/UPCED/mentoring/docs/Role-mentor.pdf>
- Larkin, Douglas (2013) *10 things to know about mentoring student teachers* <https://www.bowdoin.edu/education/pdf/ten-things-mentoring.pdf>.
- Ministry of Education Guyana (2020). *Effective Teaching Strategies for Motivating Students*. Retrieved from <https://education.gov.gy/web/index.php/teachers/tips-for-teaching/item/1478-effective-teaching-strategie>
- Reiland, D. (2019). *Six traits of great coaches and mentors*. Retrieved from <https://danreiland.com/6-traits-great-coaches-mentors>
- Shadiow, Linda (1996). Remembering a mentor. *Clearinghouse* v69 n5, 277-79.
- Victoria State Government. (2016) *A Reflective Guide to mentoring and being a teacher-mentor*. Retrieved from <https://www.education.vic.gov.au/Documents/school/teachers/profdev/Reflectiveguidetomentoringschools>.